

The Hamilton Procedure on Varying Einstein Manifolds – 8 Theory

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Abstract:

By analyzing the main equation of the framework and intersecting it with the Hamilton procedure given by the discipline of calculus of variations, the author will construct the analogous version of the momenta \dot{p}_i on varying Einstein manifolds, invoked stationary by the Euler Lagrange operator.

Introduction

In the 8T, the main equation (1) is describing a varying Einstein manifold, which is the connected manifold with (3,1) signature. The manifold was invoked stationary $M = M_0 \times R$ by an EL operator $L = (s, s', t)$ such a construction allowed us to derive equation (1.1) and the prediction of universe packets causing the outward time invariant acceleration.

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial L}{\partial s(n)} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M(1)} \frac{\partial M(1)}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial L}{\partial s(n)} \frac{\partial s(n)}{\partial M(n)} \frac{\partial M(n)}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.11)$$

$$\left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \right] \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \right] \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0$$

In the Hamilton procedure in which he presented a new set of variables, the following representation:

$$\dot{p}_i = \frac{\partial L}{\partial q_i} \quad (1.12)$$

The analogous representation of the 8T to the Hamilton procedure would be than replacement of the denominator by a varying manifold that already contain within itself the actual spatial coordinates:

$$\dot{p}_i = \frac{\partial L}{\partial s_i} \quad (1.13)$$

$$\dot{p}_i = \frac{\partial L}{\partial s_i} \frac{\partial s_i}{\partial M_i} \frac{\partial M_i}{\partial g_i} \frac{\partial g_i}{\partial t_i} \quad (1.14)$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)